

Physico-Chemical Studies of the Binding of Metal Ions with Soybean Protein. Part II. *pH*-Metric Studies in the Presence of Cu^{++} and Cd^{++}

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The binding of Cu^{++} and Cd^{++} to soybean protein has been investigated *pH*-metrically. Interaction of these ions takes place with the carboxyl as well as the imidazole group of the protein molecule. The values of $\log K$ for metal carboxyl binding are found to be 2.03 and 1.85 for Cu^{++} and Cd^{++} respectively. These values favour comparably with the $\log K$ values of the first association constants of the interaction between corresponding metal and acetate group. The $\log K$ values for metal-imidazole binding are found to be 2.34 and 2.08 for Cu^{++} and Cd^{++} respectively.

THE key role of metal ions in biochemical and physiological reactions is well established. Many physico-chemical methods, viz., light scattering, ultracentrifugation, *pH*-metric, equilibrium dialysis, polarography, etc. have been employed to know the nature of binding of the metal ions to peptides, proteins and related compounds. Such studies have not, however, been systematically undertaken in the case of proteins of vegetable origin. Recently Malik and coworkers¹⁻² had reported the results of their studies on the binding of H^+ , Zn^{++} , Mg^{++} and Mn^{++} to soybean protein with the help of hydrogen ion equilibria technique. In this communication we wish to report the results of our *pH*-metric studies on this protein in the presence of Cu^{++} and Cd^{++} .

The method of *pH*-metric titration to elucidate the number of ionisable groups in the proteins as well as to know the nature of binding of metals to them was first employed by Tanford and coworkers³⁻⁵. Later on it was successfully employed by Katchalsky and Miller⁶ to study the binding of polyelectrolyte to proteins. Recently Malik and co-workers⁷⁻⁹ have extended this method, with some variations, to elucidate the binding of metal ions of physiological importance to both fibrillar and globular proteins.

Experimental

Preparation of solutions : The soybean protein was prepared from soybean seeds (B.D.H.) by the method recommended by Suminokura¹⁰. The soybean protein has the following characteristics; the nitrogen content 7.91%, (reported 7.53%)¹¹, the ash content 5.0%, and the isoelectric *pH* 4.92. CuCl_2 and CdCl_2 (both A.R.) were used for preparing solutions in doubly distilled water and their strength were determined by EDTA titration using Eriochrome black T and murexide respectively as indicators.

Other reagents, viz., KCl, potassium hydrogen phthalate, sodium borate, acetic acid, sodium acetate, ammonia, ammonium chloride were also A.R. samples and their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. Carbonate free KOH, used as titrant was prepared by Kolthoff's method. Acetate buffer of *pH* 5.5 was prepared by mixing 0.2M solutions of acetic acid and sodium acetate. Ammonia and ammonium chloride buffer of *pH* 7.5 was prepared by mixing 1.0M solution of each.

pH measurements : These were carried out with Beckmann Model G *pH* meter, which was previously standardised by standard Beckmann buffer (*pH* 7.0) and 0.05M potassium hydrogen phthalate (*pH* 4.0) and 0.05M sodium borate (*pH* 9.20). Mixtures containing fixed amount of copper and cadmium + soybean protein or soybean protein alone were prepared with varying amounts of KOH and HCl. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.15 by the addition of KCl, and the total was made upto 10.0 ml. The *pH* was recorded immediately and after 24 hrs. Purified N_2 was passed through the reaction mixtures slowly for about 15 mins. to ensure inert atmosphere. All the measurements were made at a temperature of $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Calculations : Calculations of free H^+ and free OH^- was done by the method given by Alexander and Block¹². In this method which involves the changes in the *pH* values by the addition of certain protein concentration has been expressed by the following equation :

$$(C_1 - C_2)/g = C_1/g [1 - \text{antilog}(\Delta \text{pH})],$$

where C_1 and C_2 are the concentrations of H^+ and protein, and $\Delta \text{pH} = (\text{pH})_1 - (\text{pH})_2$; $(\text{pH})_1$ and $(\text{pH})_2$ being the *pH* values due to H^+ alone and the solution containing protein in it. The values of γ , i.e., the

number of H⁺ dissociated at a particular pH, can be obtained by subtracting the number of H⁺ bound from the total cationic groups of the protein (Table 1) for the acid range and by adding the number of hydroxyl ions bound for the basic range.

TABLE 1—IONIZABLE GROUPS IN SOYBEAN PROTEIN

Groups	Anal. Values	Observed
Side-Chain Carboxyl	—	94
Imidazole	18	18
Side-chain amino	45	46
Guanidinium	42	41
	105*	102*
[Tyrosine]/[tryptophan]	3.18	3.14

* Total cationic groups.

Results and Discussion

From the study of the titration curves of the metal soybean and soybean alone (Fig. 1), it is observed that metal have pronounced effect on the titration

EACH CURVE STARTS FROM PH 0.0

Fig. 1. Titration Curves of

1. Soybean
2. Soybean + Cu²⁺
3. Soybean + Cd²⁺

curves of soybean protein. The activity and activity coefficient of H⁺ is increased when metal ions are added to the protein as is evinced from the shift toward lower pH range in the protein metal curves. However, the changes in activity coefficient have been assumed to be negligibly small and are not considered here. The number of H⁺ thus displaced were calculated from the shift in the titration curves.

The intrinsic association constant *K* for these metal ions was calculated by Scatchard's equation¹³

$$K = \frac{V_M}{(n - V_H - V_M)C_F}$$

V_M was determined by Gurd and Murray's method¹⁴ for 1 : 1 binding and can be seen in the Table 2. The log *K* value for Cu²⁺ -carboxyl system have been calculated by using the data given in Table 2. The value of *V_H* has been taken as zero since all the carboxyl groups ionise at pH 5.50. The possibility of anion (Cl⁻ from metal salts) in the presence of a cation forming complex with the protein has been neglected because in such a case the titration curve would shift toward more acid region i.e., the acid titrated will appear abnormally strong¹⁵.

TABLE 2—BINDING DATA CALCULATED FROM TITRATION CURVES

pH	H ⁺ dissociated in absence of metal ions	H ⁺ dissociated in presence of metal ions	Difference or <i>V_M</i>	Free metal at equilibrium (<i>C_F</i>) (mM)	log <i>K</i>
Cu ²⁺ + Soybean protein system					
5.50	94.0	105.0	11.0	1.124	2.03
7.00	110.0	127.0	17.0	0.827	2.34
Cd ²⁺ + Soybean protein system					
5.50	94.0	103.0	9.0	1.379	1.85
7.00	110.0	123.0	13.0	1.103	2.08

A typical value calculated from the observed data is given below :

Now

$$K = \frac{V_M}{(n - V_H - V_M)C_F} = \frac{11.0}{(94.0 - 11.0) \times 1.1241 \times 10^{-3}}$$

$$\log K = 2.03.$$

Study of pH titration curve in the acidic region of pH reveals that metal ions in this region compete with the H⁺ for the carboxylic group of the protein. Obviously such an interaction would increase the activity of H⁺ and the number of H⁺ thus displaced would correspond to the active sites covered by the metal in this pH range. In the higher pH range, viz., pH 7.0 and above, carboxylic groups are in the basic form i.e., deprotonated and therefore the reaction between the metal and carboxyl group becomes non-competitive w.r.t. H⁺. Hence metal ions may combine with any number of fully deprotonated group without exhibiting any substantial effect on the hydrogen ion equilibria of the protein.

The interaction with the imidazole groups of the protein in neutral pH range can be explained in the light of the above discussion. Here too the number

of H^+ displaced would correspond to the number of metal ions combining with the sites occupied by the imidazole groups of the protein. The logarithm value of the intrinsic association constant for carboxyl groups with Cu^{++} is 2.03, which compares favourably with the logarithm of the first association constant between Cu^{++} and acetate nucleus¹⁴ (2.16). Similarly, the value of the logarithm of intrinsic association constant of copper imidazole¹³ resembles with the logarithm of intrinsic association constant of copper imidazole system (vide Table 3). It is well established that carboxylic group binding in case of copper is very pronounced, and, therefore, it may be expected that its affinity for the imidazole group will be sufficiently reduced. A competition between these two sites would result in a much complicated picture of interaction process of which Scatchard's equation¹³ does not take any account. The application of this equation may give slightly different values than would be expected in the absence of such competition. On the same lines, the explanation may be offered for the data of Cd^{++} -soybean system.

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF LOG K VALUES FOR METAL CARBOXYL AND METAL IMIDAZOLE SYSTEMS

Ligand	Method	log K (carboxyl)		log K (imidazole)	
		Cu^{++}	Cd^{++}	Cu^{++}	Cd^{++}
Soybean protein	pH-metric	2.03	1.85	2.34	2.08
Acetate	—	2.16	1.30	—	—
Imidazole	-	—	—	2.36	2.08

It may also be argued that at pH 5.5 the interaction will be predominantly with carboxyl and at pH 7.0 it may be predominantly due to imidazole group. This view point has been substantiated by the work of Cannan¹⁶ who found that the maximum bound ion value, in the region of pH 1.5 to pH 6.0 is attributed to the ionization of those side chain carboxyl groups not present as amides and titration between pH 6.0 and pH 8.0 is numerically identical

to the total content of basic groups, viz., guanidino, imidazole etc.

A comparison of log K values (Table 2) would reveal that copper is more strongly bound in the low pH range than Cd^{++} . It may be seen from Table 3 that the log K value for the interaction of copper ion with carboxyl group is of the same order as that of copper acetate complex, whereas log K value for cadmium ions is lower. Also, in the imidazole complex formation the order is the same as with metal carboxyl complex (Table 2).

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